

PHONETIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS AND ITS CONTENT

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Abstract. This article discusses English phonetics and its branches, proper pronunciation of the words, components of the phonetic competence and the pronunciation rules of sounds, letters, words and phonological system of the English language.

Keywords: pronunciation, phonetics, phonology, sound, letter, competence, speech, syllable, transcription, linguistic, vowel, consonant, foreign, language.

To learn to speak English correctly, you need to know the correct pronunciation. The study of speech sounds is phonetics, in this paragraph we will describe the phonetics of the English language. Learning any foreign language begins with learning its alphabet. After that, these letters are expressed and used in different words. Thus, English has 26 letters, but there are 48 sounds that are determined by these letters. The pronunciation rules of sounds, letters and corresponding words are studied by English phonetics.

Phonetics is a branch of linguistics that studies speech sounds and the sound structure of the language (syllables, sound combinations, connecting sounds in a speech chain) [Фонетика английского языка для начинающих. Электронный ресурс: Фонетика английского языка для начинающих | Enguide.ru Дата обращения: 08.12.2021.] (1.1-pic):

1.1-pic.

Content of phonetics

Like many other languages, English has experienced wide variations in pronunciation, both historically and from dialect to dialect. In general, regional dialects of English have a largely

similar (but not identical) phonological system. Phonological analysis of English often summarizes or uses one or more of these as points of reference [Ingliz fonologiyasi - English phonology. Elektron resurs: Ingliz fonologiyasi (wiki2.wiki). Murojaat sanasi: 08.12.2021.] (1.1-table):

1.1-table

English phonology

№			
1.	Phonems	consonants	sonorantlar
2.		vowels	vowel allophones
3.	leksik stress		
4.	phonotactics	joint structure	syllable-level patterns
5.			word-level patterns
6.	Prosodi	prosodik stress	
7.		rithm	
8.		intonation	
9.	history of english pronunciation		

Theoretical phonetics is a science that studies the sounds of human speech, the conditions of their formation, and their role in the design and transmission of human thought. The subject of theoretical phonetics is all forms of the sound means of the language and their functions. There are general and special phonetics. General phonetics is the formation of sound conditions depending on the pronunciation apparatus, the analysis studies the properties of sound units. Word formation, intonation, accent are studied. Specific phonetics studies analyze all of the above in a specific, individual language [Семенова Е.В. Теоретическая фонетика английского языка: учеб. пособие / Е.В. Семенова, Я.Н. Казанцева. – Красноярск: Сибирский федеральный ун-т, 2020. – 164 с. - Б. 13.]. Researchers distinguish several divisions of phonetics (see Table 1.2):

1.2-table

Departments of phonetics

№	Departments of phonetics	Contents of phonetic sections
1.	Historical phonetics	sound phenomena are considered by the language in the process of its development
2.	Physiological phonetics	learns the formation of sounds and their acoustic properties
3.	Comparative phonetics	studies the interaction of sound systems in different languages
4.	Experimental phonetics	examines the formation of sounds in the laboratory
5.	Functional phonetics	from the point of view of the function of serving human speech. studies the sound side of language

In the module of theoretical phonetics of the English language, the characteristics of English vowels and consonants and their difference from Uzbek vowels, 22 sounds of 6 vowels in English, the uniqueness of Uzbek vowels, the rules of reading vowels in English and difficulties, special features of English consonants, special features of Uzbek vowels, differences between consonants in two languages, sound - as pronunciation and hearing, letter - as writing and sight, It is known to everyone that information such as the types of vowels and the reading of vowels in English, the role of phonetic transcription in the phonetics of the English language, the difference between transcription symbols and letters, and the difference between the concept of "Sound" and

"Letter" are given. It is known from practice that the practical phonetics of the English language, as a subject of phonetics, is the study of the sound structure of the language and its components, speech organs and their functions in the production of sounds, phonemes, the principles of classification of English vowels and consonant phonemes, and the concept of transcription.

In order to have a clear and complete understanding of the essence of theoretical phonetics, phonetic phenomena can be conditionally divided into two: the segmental level, which includes the phoneme and syllable, and the word, phrase, sentence, syntagm, text o containing supersegmental level.

Phonetic competence is a person's ability to implement pronunciation norms of the language being studied in accordance with foreign language communicative competence, based on knowledge, skills, competences and relationships. [Хомутова А.А. Фонетическая компетенция: структура, содержание // Вестник ЮУрГУ. Серия: Лингвистика. 2013. - № 2. Электронный ресурс: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/foneticheskaya-kompetentsiya-struktura-soderzhanie>. Дата обращения: 10.05.2022].

According to researcher A.A. Khomutova, foreign language is a set of subcompetencies in communicative competence, which includes: (1.3-table) [Хомутова А.А. Фонетическая компетенция: структура, содержание // Вестник ЮУрГУ. Серия: Лингвистика. 2013. - № 2. Электронный ресурс: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/foneticheskaya-kompetentsiya-struktura-soderzhanie>. Дата обращения: 10.05.2022]:

1.3-jadval.

Complex of subcompetencies

№	Subkompetensiyalar	Subkompetensiyalar mazmuni
1.	linguistic competence	the ability to produce and interpret a word constructed in accordance with relevant language norms
2.	sociolinguistic competence	the ability to choose the linguistic form and the method of linguistic expression appropriate to the conditions of communication
3.	discourse competence	the ability to interpret communication texts using certain strategies and tactics
4.	socio-cultural competence	the ability to choose certain textual forms and communicative effect when used by native speakers of the language in awareness of socio-cultural contexts
5.	social competence	the ability to manage social situations in interaction with others
6.	strategic competence	the ability to use verbal and non-verbal means to compensate for insufficient knowledge

In the formation of phonetic competence, the interaction of communicators and their mutual understanding, as well as the fact that phonetic competence affects all components of foreign language communicative competence, is considered important. [Хомутова А.А. Фoneticheskaya kompetentsiya: struktura, sodержanie // Vestnik YuUrGU. Seriya: Lingvistika. 2013. - № 2. Elektronnyy resurs: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/foneticheskaya-kompetentsiya-struktura-soderzhanie>. Data obrasheniya: 10.05.2022] (1.4-table):

1.4-table

The effect of phonetic competence on subcompetencies

№	Subcompetencies	Effect of phonetic competence
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1.	linguistic competence	knowledge of the articulatory base of the language being studied, the structure of speech organs, the mechanism of voice formation, prosody, intonation, basic phonetic phenomena and terms; to know the ways of articulation of sounds in the native language, for example, to know the similarity / difference of sounds, to know the types of intonation that allow to avoid interference in the acquisition of foreign pronunciation; knowledge of formal or informal speech styles, dialects; the ability to apply knowledge in practice, to make statements that meet the goals and conditions of communication
2.	sociolinguistic competence	influencing the choice of phonetic forms depending on age, social status, level of education, etc.;; the ability to apply knowledge in the practice of communication where mutual understanding has been achieved
3.	discourse competence	construction of speech movements using emotional means (intonation, pause, emphasis, rhythm).
4.	socio-cultural competence	to know the place and role of phonetic means in understanding and repeating speech; knowledge of the literary standard of pronunciation; knowing pronunciation options, using them in appropriate situations, communication; to know the similarities and differences in the phonetic system of the mother tongue and foreign languages; the ability to observe the pronunciation of speakers
5.	social competence	the ability to understand and repeat speech pronunciation according to the purpose and conditions of communication; the ability to adapt to the standards of speech culture in a foreign language
6.	strategic competence	phonetic knowledge aimed at mastering lexical and grammatical structures; the ability to know the lexical and grammatical structures in the speech stream

It consists of 4 components of phonetic competence, i.e. cognitive, pragmatic, reflexive and socio-cultural structural components [Хомутова А.А. Фонетическая компетенция: структура, содержание // Вестник ЮУрГУ. Серия: Лингвистика. 2013. - № 2. Электронный ресурс: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/foneticheskaya-kompetentsiya-struktura-soderzhanie>. Дата обращения: 10.05.2022] (1.5-table):

1.5-table

Components of phonetic competence

№	Components of phonetic competence	Phonetic phenomena
1.	The cognitive component represents readiness for communicative and mental activity aimed at becoming	perception and imitation through practical knowledge; distinguishing the images of individual events or methods, their use in language tools in the form of rules (knowledge of language theory);

	a meaningful topic of communication	the relationship between the graphs and their phonemic environments, the application of the knowledge established in the rules; the use of images for the receptive use of international phonetic transcription symbols in determining pronunciation according to dictionary information
2.	Pragmatic component - represents preparation for the transfer of communicative content in a communication situation	It is defined in the conversational strategies of speech as follows: phonetic skills in reception; phonetic skills in production; phonetic strategies in reception; phonetic strategies in production
3.	The reflexive component is closely related to the acquisition of self-control skills, self-correction, emotional evaluation of the studied material, as well as the acquisition of educational and research strategies. represents	Different approaches to determining self-management: a) personality traits; b) mental activity of a person (manifestation and development of self-awareness, thinking, intellectual qualities, criticality, discipline); c) as a component of the student's educational activity, to analyze and regulate its progress and results; d) ability to manage one's own activities and correct mistakes. the composition of self-management: 1) introducing students to the purpose of the activity and its understanding; 2) introducing the final result and the ways to achieve it; 3) comparison of the achieved result; 4) assessment of the status of completed works; 5) identifying and analyzing errors, determining their causes; 6) correction of work based on self-assessment
4.	Socio-cultural component - based on the comparative analysis of the phonetic systems of the native language and foreign languages, the use of the specific features of pronunciation, the cultural norms of the language in accordance with the speech represent the understanding and pronunciation	cultural diversity, pronunciation variability, differences in socio-cultural norms, formal and informal phonetic devices and cultural patterns of pronunciation styles; knowing the socio-cultural context, mastering cultural norms and manners, choosing phonetic means in the context of socio-cultural speech; knowledge of dialect forms, methods of phonetic description of languages; it is carried out on the basis of the principles of selection and methodical organization of the background material

Considering phonetics as an aspect of learning, we define it as the sound system of the language, the sum of all the sound means of the language: sounds, sound combinations, syllables, syntagms, syntagm, rhythm, tone, intonation. The process of forming the phonetic component of language competence requires a certain flexibility, the development of the child's articulation apparatus, good phonemic and intonation (slux) hearing, therefore, in the conditions of mass education, the phonetics of a foreign language is better mastered by children aged 4-5 years, and then minimum communicative competence in the mother tongue is formed from the knowledge (Фонетический компонент языковой компетенции. Электронный ресурс: Фонетический

компонент языковой компетенции - МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ (studme.org). Дата обращения: 15.07.2022).

As a necessary condition for practical knowledge of a foreign language, the methods of successful professional activity in the conditions of modern social development, learning a foreign language in professionally oriented fields, and increasing the level of professional language training in the future are analyzed. (Устинова Н.П. Формирование и совершенствование фонетической компетенции студентов технических специальностей. Электронный ресурс: phonetic-competence.pdf (internationalconference.ru). Дата обращения: 15.07.2022).

Phonetics is what we say, while phonology is the unscientific understanding of how we do it. David Crystal's book "Cambridge Encyclopedia of the English Language" contains a poem that proves the above point: "it ain't what you say, it's the way you say it." Phonology deals with the beautiful systematization and registration of speech sounds, turning them into correct and effective communication. Phonological competence is a sub-competency of the communicative competence of a foreign language, and along with phonetic competence, it plays a functionally important role, because language as a means of communication manifests itself in sound, sound behavior that determines productivity and success or, on the contrary, against and low efficiency studies the effect of directed speech (Швецова Е.О. Формирование фонологической компетенции у студентов языковых вузов, изучающих английский язык как второй иностранный: Дис. ... магист. acad. степен. – Челябинск, 2020. – 131 с. – Б. 15-16.).

However, it should be noted that the process of formation and improvement of phonetic skills should not be limited to the initial stage of learning a foreign language. During the foreign language, phonetic material is selected and distributed, so that sounds, sound combinations, stress, rhythmic patterns of words, tone and intonation constructions are studied at each stage of the training, this is the acquisition of phonetic material and the development of phonetic skills. emphasizes the importance of formation (Фонетический компонент языковой компетенции. Электронный ресурс: Фонетический компонент языковой компетенции - МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ (studme.org). Дата обращения: 15.07.2022).

The phonetic component of language competence is formed as follows:

to know the specific features of the articulation of sounds in a foreign language (vowels and consonants, sound combinations, diphthongs, triphthongs) and its phonetic system in general; knowledge of transcription and transcription reading skills;

to know the rules of pronunciation of sounds in the flow of speech (for example, assimilation, pronunciation of sounds) and use of intonation models, rules of stress in a separate word, rhythmic group, phrase, rules of syntagmatic articulation of phrases, rules of articulation;

phonetic skills (Фонетический компонент языковой компетенции. Электронный ресурс: Фонетический компонент языковой компетенции - МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ (studme.org). Дата обращения: 15.07.2022).

In short, it allows to identify different cases of phonological competence and phonetic components of language competence in understanding the essence of phonetic competence.

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